

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

TRANSACTIONS BASED ON ONTOLOGY MODELS

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Annotatsiya. This paper analyzes the mathematical support of the module, which helps to create queries based on intelligent communication systems, and formulates the main results that will help to formulate further research. Based on the request, the answer is transacted. These are key concepts in knowledge management. A single node of a communication scenario corresponds to a single node of intelligent communication systems.

Keywords: Ontology, methods of knowledge expression, knowledge base, database, facts, events, queries, property, event, object, graphs.

Introduction

One of the main tasks of the concept of "artificial intelligence", which is becoming part of information technology and society, is to perform comprehensible thinking operations using computer systems and their technical devices. It consists in creating a real real process of interaction between human actions and the computer (computers) [1, 2].

Communication systems can be used to create a user query in library systems. This requires the methods of artificial intelligence-based software modules, architectures appropriate to that style, information flow models, communication methods, and algorithms to assist users in creating or shaping the queries outlined in the previous section.

Based on the above architectures, the following can be suggested as mathematical support for building an intellectual environment and making decisions in it:

1. Mathematical support of the decision-making hierarchy based on formal logical knowledge;
2. Mathematical software based on logical semantic connections and production knowledge;
3. Frame knowledge-based mathematical software;
4. Mathematical support based on the construction of ontological knowledge.

It is necessary to build an intellectual environment for the formation of queries and to identify methods of intellectual processing based on ontological knowledge in it.

The expression of ontologies is important to ensure that there is natural communication when

creating queries. It is expedient to construct ontologies for each object of the Library systems and to determine the mutual proximity of these objects, to combine the objects.

It has been found that the repetition of the architectural process makes it possible to implement an individual approach in communication systems. That is, the basic communication methods of communication systems are based on:

1. Question - answer;
2. Targeted communication;
3. Purposeless communication;

This requires the construction of ontologies for each PS, the creation of intellectual communication scenarios for the organization of communication in communication systems, as well as methods for determining the proximity of their objects.

Research methodology

Building an ontology of corporate information library objects serves to express knowledge and create an intellectual environment. In the intellectual environment, decision-making is based on the intellectual processing of data. From this point of view, in order to create communication systems that facilitate the formation of queries, copies of intellectual environment classes, i.e., working with objects, should cover all aspects of thinking in relation to the object [1].

The construction of an ontology for a predmed field is understood on the basis of the following trinity:

$$O = \langle X, R, F \rangle$$

Here $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, $n = |X|$;

$R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k, \dots, r_m\}$, $R : x_1 \times x_2 \times \dots \times x_n$, $m = |R|$ - the number of interactions of given class objects in the subject area. These serve to create a pattern for the interaction of classes. In general, class relations are divided into general relations (rules are created, in part, on the basis of definite relations) and definite, definite relations;

$F: X \times R$ - a limited set of functions that interprets given classes and / or relationships. In special cases it is used as a set of interpretive functions to create a broad glossary, dictionary, i.e. x classes;

The method of constructing an ontology for a subject area consists of two steps:

1. Conduct preliminary analysis for the subject area and determine the characteristics for class characteristics;

2. Build an ontograph model for the subject area. In this case, the ontograph is a graphic, the ends of which are the classes (objects) of the subject area, and the arcs are the relationship between them. A graph is a one-way oriented graph with several arcs entering and exiting one of the three.

The first stage. When constructing an ontology, two types of properties are used for the subject area, and they differ from each other:

-Property value. This is the relationship between the classes created and the data type or character types;

-Property-object. This is the relationship between the two classes created.

The second stage. We construct a PS ontology using a data model based on an obscure hypergraph to construct a model in the form of a graph. Here are the basic concepts and explanations to formalize this.

Ontology is a very complex data structure that requires imaging using special mathematical hardware [3]. We propose to apply a binary approach to processing ontological knowledge based on the use of an obscure hypergraphic data model for PS. The ontology to be constructed is an obscure ontology (explicit ontology is an obscure ontology is a special case).

Analysis and results

While each of the objects is defined with a certain degree of belonging to a common class, in a general obscure class, this group of objects merges.

From this, the general nonlinear class can be thought of as the arc of the obscure hypergraph,

with the ends included in the generalized arc forming the general nonlinear class. However, in the construction of the ontology, the order of the elements, the rules of the relationship between the objects, and the direction of the relationship are important. Therefore, the first type of obscure-oriented hypergraph is included in the obscure hypergraphic data model.

The first type is a vaguely oriented hypergraph $\tilde{H} = (X, D)$ and $X = \{x_i\}, i \in I, I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $D = \{\check{d}_j\}, j \in J, J = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ a set of obscurely oriented bows. In this case, for each arc, there is the following (1) obscure set [3].

$$\check{d}_j = \left(\left(\frac{\mu_{a_j}(x_{i_1})}{x_{i_1}} \right), \left(\frac{\mu_{a_j}(x_{i_2})}{x_{i_2}} \right), \dots, \left(\frac{\mu_{a_j}(x_{i_m})}{x_{i_m}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$\tilde{H}$ each of the hypergraphs d_j The obscure arc follows the obscurely oriented graph $\tilde{G}(d_j) = (X, \tilde{U}_j)$ represented in the form. This graph, too $\tilde{H}$ has as many three as there are three in the hypergraph. Also $\tilde{H} = (X, D)$ the hypergraph is also treated in the same way as a graph with a blunt-pointed tip. Such an arbitrary obscure ontology can be represented in the form of an obscure triangular oriented graph based on expression (1) (Fig. 1), i.e.

$$O \rightarrow \tilde{X}(H) = (X, \tilde{U}) = \bigcup_{\check{d}_j \in D} \tilde{G}(d_j)$$

Figure 1. $\tilde{O}(H)$ is a nonlinear end-oriented graph model for subject-oriented ontology.

From this there is a class A atomic set that is cross-linked with the R relation. In this case, the correctly structured set of terms of the ontological classification language L is defined as follows:

1. If $x \in A$, $x \in L$;
2. If $x \in L$, $r_i \in R$ and $y_i \in L, i = 1, \dots, n$ $x[r_1: y_1, \dots, r_n: y_n] \in L$

The basic approach of ontology is a simple taxonomically incorporated approach. On this basis we can generalize the concept of

transitivity to all relations between properly structured ends (classes).

$\tilde{O}(H)$ what an ontological graph $x, y \in X$ the ontological relationship of the ends allows the introduction of the concept of an uncertain route directed by $M(x, y)$. Henceforth, the directed nonlinear route is the nonlinear route, which is oriented from x three to y three along the graph arcs [4].

Intelligent communication scenario construction systems are based on ontology-based question-and-answer methods, as described in the top paragraphs. Question-answer methods are mainly database-oriented and are distinguished by two features. The first is based on the definition of roles in this communication process, for example, when the user is in the role of the requester, while the software module plays the role of the respondent. In the second, the answers to the questions are formed on a key-value basis [6].

Such approaches are used in many software packages, such as DEDUCOM. This program is a special case of Lisp-programming modules using algorithms for building fact-based communication scenarios. The rules for drawing conclusions based on lisp expressions are as follows:

$$R: ((X \rightarrow V) \wedge (V \rightarrow Y)) \Rightarrow f: (X \rightarrow Y)$$

As a result of research, the scenarios of intellectual communication is a cyclical process, the elements of which are considered on the basis of nodes, its two transition schemes are direct transition, conditional transition.

Figure 3. Node-to-node diagram of intellectual communication scenarios.

In this case, N - nodes, ie N_{k-1} incoming question, N_k outgoing answer, questions corresponding to the node in the database - li ($i = 1, .. n$) and a formalized view of the answers corresponding to the node ti ($i = 1, .. n$).

Intelligent communication scenarios are based on the following rule for direct transition in the node-to-node scheme:

$$NODE: \left(R: \left(Q \left(node: \left(N_{k-1} \rightarrow N_{k-1}^{l_j} \right) \right) \right) \right) ? A(N_k^{t_i}): A(N_k^{t_n}) \rightarrow N_{k+1},$$

$$j = 1, \dots, n, i = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Here $A(N_k^{t_n})$ is the most universal answer to the question posed. Therefore, if no suitable answer is found to the question, this most universal answer is used. n is the number of options corresponding to the question.

Intelligent communication scenarios are based on the following rule for passing through a condition in a node-passing scheme:

$$NODE: \left(R: \left(\left(\exists Q \left(node: \left(N_{k-1} \rightarrow N_{k-1}^{l_j} \right) \right) \right) \wedge \left(\forall Q \left(node: \left(N_c \rightarrow N_c^{l_j} \right) \right) \right) \right) ? A(N_k^{t_i}): A(N_k^{t_n}) \right) \rightarrow N_{k+1},$$

$$j = 1, \dots, n, \quad c = 1, \dots, m \ll k - 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Here $A(N_k^{t_n})$ the most universal answer to the given question and the number of options corresponding to the n -question.

It can be seen from the above transition diagrams that in intellectual communication scenarios, addressing the questions before the current question determines its question memory availability and the purpose of the communication and creates the desired query for the user.

In order to achieve the desired query, the following conditions must be met for the scenarios used in communication systems:

1. The purpose of the communication scenario process can be achieved in limited transactions, and with the onset of problem solving, all the questions and answers necessary for the formation of these transactions are identified;

2. Changing the set of expected answers always creates a new set that is different from the current one.

From these conditions, the method of constructing intellectual communication scenarios based on the Mili machine [5] can be written on the basis of the following five.

$$D = (Q, A, T, f, g) \quad (2)$$

where D denotes the communication scenario.

$$Q = \{q_i\}; i = 1, \dots, k$$

In the communication scenario method, it represents a set of stable states of the automaton and corresponds to a set of names of the

communication record. Unlike a communication protocol transaction, a communication scenario transaction includes a single question and all possible answers. A steady state is a state of waiting for an active communication node to respond to a reactive communication node or a state of waiting for a reactive communication node to ask a question to an active communication node [6].

$$f: (T \times A) \rightarrow T$$

This refers to the transition function and is the transition from the previous scenario to the new state scenario (new transaction of the scenario). In this case, the action is performed depending on the ID of the current transaction and the response received from the reactive communication node.

$$g: (T \times A) \rightarrow Q$$

Specifies the output function, which determines the ID of the next question, the ID of the current transaction, and the current response of the reactive communication node.

The transition and exit functions correspond to the classical definition of a national machine gun. The transaction function is natural when modeling a memory access method. Therefore, it uses the φ function instead of the f and g functions.

$$\varphi: (T \times A) \rightarrow (T \times Q)$$

Hence, the transaction function identifies the pair. Defines the name of the next question and the name of the transaction, the current answer, and the name of the current transaction [6].

When performing a transaction (transition from the previous stable state to the next state), the model of the machine can be determined as follows.

$$D = (Q, A, T, \varphi)$$

This expression performs the following sequence of events:

- Accept current response;
- Understand the current answer Determine the name of the next question by the degree of relevance m .

If there is no defined response A structure in any way, this means that in order to recognize the current response, the D communication scenario must relate activity to all elements of the A response set during each transaction. The place of this set is important for scripts.

The expression of the description of the automatic model, which has the property of

remembering the answers of the intellectual communication scenario, has two purposes. They are:

-first, an assessment of how useful the proposed automated model access to a set of questions is in building a communicative scenario method;

-second, the communication provides a transition to the next network model of the scenario method and consists of identification. For example, $T = \{t_i\}, i \in I, I \in (1, \dots, 4)$ reflect the logic of moving to the next question of an active communication scenario involving four transactions and in response to the understood and misunderstood responses of the communication scenario.

t_2 the transaction generates a corresponding Q2 question based on the active communication scenario Q1 question reshaping. t_2 in the transaction t_1 expects to receive answers to the questions in the transaction. Also, answer A_2 serves to create a request to return to transaction t_1 and Q1 to repeat the question.

The mathematical model of a machine gun with the ability to remember the answers of an intellectual communication scenario is expressed as follows.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q &= \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4\} \\ A &= \{A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5\} \\ T &= \{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4\} \\ \varphi: (t_1, A_1) &\rightarrow (t_1, Q_1) \\ \varphi: (t_1, A_3) &\rightarrow (t_3, Q_3) \\ \varphi: (t_1, A_4) &\rightarrow (t_4, Q_4) \\ \varphi: (t_1, A_5) &\rightarrow (t_2, Q_2) \\ \varphi: (t_2, A_1) &\rightarrow (t_2, Q_2) \\ \varphi: (t_2, A_2) &\rightarrow (t_1, Q_1) \\ \varphi: (t_2, A_3) &\rightarrow (t_3, Q_3) \\ \varphi: (t_2, A_4) &\rightarrow (t_4, Q_4) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

φ the transaction function (3), represented by the function, describes the logic of access to the set of questions on the one hand, and in this sense can be considered as a mathematical model of the method of access to the set of questions, on the other hand.

Conclusion

The mathematical support of the module, which facilitates the creation of queries based on intelligent communication systems, was analyzed and the main results were formed, which will help to formulate further research. It was found that the repetition of the architectural process could

implement an individual approach in communication systems, and that the main communication methods were question-answer, targeted communication, and non-targeted communication. The method of constructing the ontology for the subject area was analyzed, the $\tilde{O}$

(H) nonlinear end-oriented graph model for the ontology designed for PS, and the mathematical representation of the automated model with the feature of remembering the answers of the intellectual communication scenario were developed.

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